

NOTTINGHAM TRENT UNIVERSITY

**SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODELLING OF NEOTROPICAL
XENARTHANS (MAMMALIA: XENARTHRA): A SYSTEMATIC
REVIEW AND CASE STUDY ON TAMANDUAS (MYRMECOPHAGIDAE:
TAMANDUA)**

by

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Paper One

XENARTHANS (MAMMALIA: XENARTHRA) IN THE NEOTROPICS: A
SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODELS

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Abstract

Species Distribution Models (SDMs) are widely used in conservation biology to predict species' ranges, particularly as climate change continues to threaten habitat availability. The application of SDMs to biodiversity hotspots, such as the Neotropics, is crucial for preserving species richness and endemism. Xenarthrans, a mammalian superorder comprising sloths, anteaters and armadillos, are ecologically significant and susceptible to climate change, although they are relatively understudied in ecological modelling.

This systematic literature review assessed how SDMs have been applied to xenarthrans in the Neotropics, with a focus on taxa studied, environmental predictors used, and their application to conservation. A systematic search on two databases, Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus, identified 22 peer-reviewed studies. Brazil and the giant anteater (*Myrmecophaga tridactyla*) were found to be the focus of several SDM studies. The southern tamandua (*Tamandua tetradactyla*) and the giant armadillo (*Priodontes maximus*) were also frequently modelled, often in pairs with the giant anteater. Closely related taxa were not often modelled together. WorldClim was the most common source of predictors, usually at a 5 km resolution, and occurrence data mainly came from literature and field surveys. There was a lack of standardisation with variable selection for the same species, though the precipitation of the warmest quarter was often cited as the most important predictor for several xenarthran species.

Conservation status was mentioned in the majority of the reviewed studies; however, fewer than half of the studies linked their findings to Protected Area (PA) coverage. Geographic bias towards countries with greater research capacity and taxonomic bias towards large and charismatic species were evident. Functionally similar species were occasionally modelled together, while Data Deficient species were modelled less frequently; this highlights the need

for more field studies and data collection. Integrated SDM databases (iSDMdb) could aid in the synthesis of SDM outputs and encourage conservation efforts to be more holistic.

Introduction

Species Distribution Models (SDMs) are a tool used to predict species' geographic ranges and assess habitat suitability (Murphy and Smith, 2021). SDMs are frequently used to predict species' ranges in response to climate change (Peterson and Soberon, 2012), which enables proactive conservation planning and research (Gomes et al., 2018). SDMs are rooted in the ecological niche theory (Pasanisi et al., 2024); a niche is a multi-dimensional space, where the dimensions represent the environmental conditions that a species relies on for survival (Hutchinson, 1957). As such, the ecological accuracy of SDMs depends upon the relevance of the environmental predictors chosen (Elith and Leathwick, 2009) and their corresponding resolutions (Cohen and Jetz, 2024). Various SDM methods exist and can be categorised as correlative or mechanistic. Correlative SDMs, such as MaxEnt, are ideal for poorly studied taxa as they identify statistical relationships between species occurrence and environmental variables (Srivastava, Lafond, and Griess, 2019). Alternatively, mechanistic SDMs are more predictive as they incorporate the species' physiology and its interaction with the environment into the model (Kearney and Porter, 2009). Despite the necessity of mechanistic models (Urban et al., 2016), correlative models are predominantly used as they have low physiological data requirements and presence-only occurrence points are easily accessible (Higgins, et al., 2020). This review focuses on the most frequently used SDM techniques: correlative methods.

The Neotropics are among the most biodiverse regions in the world (Myers et al., 2000), extending from southern Mexico to South America (Antonelli et al., 2018). This hotspot is a conservation priority as the biodiversity is declining rapidly due to anthropogenic impact and the progression of climate change (Antonelli, 2021). The extensive species richness and diversity in this region emphasise the need for research that informs wildlife conservation

(Kamino et al., 2012). SDMs have been demonstrated to address knowledge gaps within ecology (Guisan et al., 2013), which makes them particularly valuable in the Neotropics. Xenarthran species remain relatively underrepresented in ecological modelling (Superina and Loughry, 2015) despite their evolutionary distinctiveness (Isaac et al., 2007) and ecological significance (McDonald, 2005; Rodrigues et al., 2019). Conservation is a concern for this superorder, as they represent a whole lineage of placental mammals, and consist of only 31 extant species (Superina and Loughry, 2015). Low detection rates (Desbiez et al., 2024), uneven data availability (Santos et al., 2019) and the elusive nature of these species (Voss, 2019) all contribute to their underrepresentation in research. Xenarthrans play key roles in ecosystem functioning (Desbiez and Kluyber, 2013), including bioturbation (Feijo et al., 2022), and seed dispersal (Vaz et al., 2012). As xenarthrans depend on minimally disturbed habitats (Di Blanco et al., 2022), occupy specialised ecological niches (Abba and Cassini, 2010) and have low reproductive rates (Fromme et al., 2023), this superorder is particularly vulnerable to habitat degradation and climate change. SDMs have proven effective when applied to xenarthrans, as they have successfully guided conservation planning by refining species distributions and highlighting Priority Areas (PAs; Ferraz et al., 2021). It is crucial to expand the application of SDMs to xenarthran species to improve conservation outcomes across the Neotropics.

This systematic literature review aims to critically evaluate the application of SDMs on xenarthran species in the Neotropics. In light of the ecological importance, vulnerability, and underrepresentation of these species in spatial modelling, this review aims to identify trends, biases, and gaps in the current literature by conducting a structured synthesis of peer-reviewed studies identified via databases, namely Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus. This review also aims to examine geographic and taxonomic focus, data sources, environmental variables, and their application to conservation.

Methods

Search Strategy and Databases

The PRISMA 2020 statement (Page et al., 2021) was used throughout this review to ensure that scientific standards were maintained. A systematic literature search was conducted on 1 April 2025 and implemented across two scientific databases, WoS and Scopus, to ensure comprehensive coverage of relevant ecological research. The search terms and Boolean operators were designed to capture the key aspects of the research question; thus, the terms were grouped into three categories: (1) modelling terminology, (2) geographic regions within the Neotropics, and (3) the target genus (see Table 1). The selection of modelling terminology was guided by a preliminary scan of available literature, based on its frequent use and applicability in research. In both databases, the search was limited to terms appearing in the title, abstract, or keywords to increase the relevance of retrieved studies; in WoS, this restriction is referred to as “Topic”. A publication date filter was applied, narrowing the scope from 2000 to 2025; this reflects the period of SDM advancement and ensures this review is relevant to current modelling techniques.

Selection Criteria

Table 1. Database search query. The search terms were grouped into 3 categories: (1) modelling terminology relevant to SDMs, (2) geographic regions within the Neotropics and (3) the target genus, comprising all extant genera in the xenarthran superorder. The search terms of each category were combined using the Boolean operator **OR**; **AND** was used to link the logic of the three categories. The asterisk (*) was used as a truncation symbol to capture multiple word endings.

Databases	Search input
Web of Science, Scopus	((("model*" OR "species distribution" OR "species distribution model*" OR "habitat suitab*" OR "ecological niche" OR "habitat model*" OR "MaxEnt" OR "Bioclim" OR "GARP" OR "ensemble" OR "ecological modelling" OR "niche modelling" OR "predictive model*" OR "SDM") AND ("South America" OR "South American" OR "Neotropic*" OR "Amazon*" OR "Andes" OR "Argentina" OR "Bolivia" OR "Brazil" OR "Chile" OR "Colombia" OR "Ecuador" OR "French Guiana" OR "Guyana" OR "Paraguay" OR "Peru" OR "Suriname" OR "Uruguay" OR "Venezuela") AND ("Xenarthra" OR "Pilosa" OR "Cingulata" OR "sloth" OR "anteater" OR "armadillo" OR "Bradypus" OR "Choloepus" OR "Cyclopes" OR "Tamandua" OR "Myrmecophaga" OR "Dasypus" OR "Cabassous" OR "Euphractus" OR "Chaetophractus" OR "Zaedyus" OR "Tolypeutes" OR "Calyptophractus" OR "Chlamyphorus" OR "Priodontes"))

This review only considered studies that met a predefined set of inclusion criteria, which ensured their alignment with the research objectives. All eligible studies focused on countries or areas within the Neotropical region and assessed xenarthran species, either individually or as part of a multi-species ecological analysis. To maintain consistency in modelling approaches, only studies that employed correlative SDMs were considered. Moreover, studies were required to report on the environmental predictor variables used in the modelling process. Only peer-reviewed publications written in English were included, and each study

needed to provide sufficient methodological detail to allow the extraction of relevant data.

Studies were excluded if they used occupancy data rather than occurrence data to retain focus on presence-based correlative SDMs.

Screening Process

All papers retrieved from the initial database search query were subjected to a screening process (Figure 1). Upon removing duplicates using a platform called “Rayaan” (Ouzzani et al., 2016), the records were screened. The titles and abstracts were reviewed for relevance to the research question. Theoretical papers, reviews and inaccessible publications were excluded at this stage. Subsequently, a thorough reading of each article was conducted and assessed against the inclusion criteria to assess eligibility.

Quantitative Synthesis

The data were extracted by a single reviewer (SBK), organised using Excel and visualised using R 4.4.1 (R Core Team, 2024). Patterns and trends were identified across study years, geographic focus, taxonomic coverage, species co-occurrence, data sources, environmental predictors, and conservation applications. Co-occurrence patterns between species and predictor variable usage were also explored to assess the extent of methodological consistency across studies.

Results

A total of 319 studies were retrieved during the initial search process, though following screening and eligibility assessment, only 22 studies were included in this review (Figure 1).

The full list of the literature included in this review is presented in Appendix Table 1.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram illustrating the study selection process. Diagram produced using the PRISMA2020 R package and Shiny app (Haddaway et al., 2022).

Temporal and Geographic Scope

The earliest publications retrieved by the search (spanning 2000 to 2025) appeared in 2006, although there was a noticeable increase in relevant publications in 2012. The volume of studies remained steady through the mid-2010s, peaking in 2022 ($n_{\text{reports}} = 7$; Figure 2A).

Among the countries represented, Brazil was the most frequently studied ($n_{\text{reports}} = 11$; Figure 2B).

Out of 22 studies, 16 (72.7%) focused on a single country, while 4 (18.2%) focused on a particular ecoregion. 1 (4.5%) study focused on occurrence data from multiple countries, and the remaining study (4.5%) focused on species ranges.

Figure 2. Number of reviewed studies published over time (A); and number of reviewed studies per country/region within the Neotropics (B). (Note: Some studies included multiple countries; therefore, the counts per country are not mutually exclusive or additive).

Species Coverage

Excluding the broad-scale assessment by Feijo et al. (2022), a total of 31 xenarthran species were identified across the remaining reviewed studies; representation was heavily skewed (Figure 3). The giant anteater (*Myrmecophaga tridactyla*) was the most frequently studied species ($n_{\text{reports}} = 7$), followed by the southern tamandua (*Tamandua tetradactyla*), the nine-banded armadillo (*Dasyus novemcinctus*), and the giant armadillo (*Priodontes maximus*), each appearing in 5 studies. In contrast, 16 species appeared in only 1 study, including the northern tamandua (*Tamandua mexicana*), and several long-nosed and hairy armadillo species.

Figure 3. Occurrence of xenarthran species in the reviewed studies. The study by Feijo et al. (2022) was excluded from this figure as the species were not named.

Among the 22 studies reviewed, 11 (50%) focused exclusively on a single xenarthran species rather than multiple taxa (Figure 4). The greater naked-tailed armadillo (*Cabassous tatouay*) and the giant anteater were the most frequently targeted taxa in single-species studies. No recurring combinations of species were observed across multi-species studies (Appendix Figure 1).

Figure 4. Species that were the focus of a single-species study and the number of times they were the focus of a study.

Pairwise species co-occurrence patterns (Figure 5) showed that most xenarthran species were modelled together only once across studies. High co-occurrence frequencies ($n_{\text{reports}} = 3$) were limited to a small subset of species, particularly the giant anteater and the southern tamandua, and the giant anteater and the giant armadillo. Closely related species such as the maned sloth (*Bradypus torquatus*) and the brown-throated sloth (*Bradypus variegatus*), as well as the southern tamandua and the northern tamandua, co-occurred in only 1 study each. Sloths were generally modelled less frequently and rarely modelled alongside other xenarthrans.

Studies that focused on Brazil and Argentina demonstrated high taxonomic diversity, with SDMs in each country representing species from all three major clades: armadillos, sloths, and anteaters (Appendix Figure 2). Argentine studies had a high representation of armadillos, including the pink fairy armadillo (*Chlamyphorus truncatus*). Fewer species were studied in countries such as Bolivia, Costa Rica, Mexico, and Suriname; however, these countries may be included in studies with broader geographic scopes.

Figure 5. Pairwise species co-occurrence in multi-species studies. The heatmap shows how often each pair of xenarthran species appeared together across the reviewed studies. Darker cells indicate a higher frequency of co-occurrence, with a maximum of 3 shared appearances. The study by Feijo et al. (2022) was excluded from this figure as the species were not named.

Data Inputs

WorldClim (Fick and Hijmans, 2017) was the most commonly used source of environmental predictor data ($n_{\text{reports}} = 11$; Figure 6A), followed by the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM; Farr et al., 2007; $n_{\text{reports}} = 5$). WorldClim was the sole predictor source in 4 reports, while 7 others combined it with additional datasets. Predictor sources that were used only once include the INPE database (Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais; 2023), PaleoClim (Brown et al., 2018), MapBiomas Project (2023) and others.

Occurrence data were most frequently sourced from literature ($n_{\text{reports}} = 11$) and field surveys ($n_{\text{reports}} = 11$; Figure 6B). Field-derived data came from a variety of methods, including a watershed survey ($n_{\text{reports}} = 1$), general observations ($n_{\text{reports}} = 6$), camera trap studies ($n_{\text{reports}} = 2$), a road-kill study ($n_{\text{reports}} = 1$) and an interview ($n_{\text{reports}} = 1$). GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility; 2023) was also used in several studies ($n_{\text{reports}} = 6$), serving as a key source of occurrence data. 1 study did not disclose the origin of its occurrence data.

Figure 6. Frequency of environmental predictor data sources used across studies (A); and frequency of occurrence data sources used to build SDMs (B). Multiple sources could be used in a single study. Only sources used in ≥ 2 studies are shown. Abbreviations: SRTM – Shuttle Radar Topography Mission; DEM – Digital Elevation Model; USGS – United States Geological Survey; GIS – Geographical Information System; GBIF – Global Biodiversity Information Facility.

The number of occurrence records used per species varied considerably across studies (Figure 7). Whilst most studies used between 50 and 500 records per species, some notable outliers were observed. 1 study modelling the nine-banded armadillo used 2348 occurrence records, whereas studies modelling the greater naked-tailed armadillo and the Andean hairy armadillo used 9 occurrence records. Across the subset of studies included in Figure 7, the median number of occurrence records was 115.

Figure 7. Number of occurrence records used for xenarthran species across studies where such data were reported. Only species included in ≥ 2 studies and with available record counts in ≥ 2 studies are shown. Each bar represents the number of records used in a single study. Note: Some species appear fewer times here than in earlier figures due to missing record counts in certain studies. The study by Feijo et al. (2022) was excluded from this figure as the species were not named.

The majority of studies used data with resolutions of 5 km or finer (Appendix Figure 3), indicating a general preference for high-resolution environmental layers. Only 18% of studies employed coarser resolutions (> 5 km).

Several predictor variables were repeatedly applied to the same species across different studies. Elevation and mean diurnal range were used in models of the giant anteater, while altitude was used in studies for both the giant armadillo and the greater naked-tailed armadillo. Annual mean temperature featured in studies for the nine-banded armadillo and the southern three-banded armadillo (*Tolypeutes matacus*). Temperature seasonality was used in studies for the silky anteater (*Cyclopes didactylus*). No predictor variable was applied to the same species in more than 2 studies.

Multiple predictor variables were identified as important across many xenarthran species (Table 2). Precipitation of the warmest quarter was the most commonly reported important predictor of species distribution ($n_{\text{species}} = 9$), including for the giant anteater and the southern tamandua. This was followed by temperature seasonality ($n_{\text{species}} = 6$) and precipitation seasonality ($n_{\text{species}} = 5$). Other frequently cited important predictors included precipitation of the driest month ($n_{\text{species}} = 4$) and elevation ($n_{\text{species}} = 4$). Among all species-important predictor pairs, only 2 were reported more than once. Annual mean temperature was identified as an important predictor for the giant anteater ($n_{\text{reports}} = 2$), and precipitation of the driest month was reported as important for the greater naked-tailed armadillo ($n_{\text{reports}} = 2$). No other species-important predictor pair was repeated across studies.

Table 2. Summary of the most frequently reported important environmental predictor variables across SDM studies of xenarthrans. Variables listed were considered important for ≥ 2 different species' distributions.

Predictor	Species	No. Species
Precipitation of warmest quarter	Giant anteater, Southern tamandua, Nine-banded armadillo, Yepes long-nosed armadillo, Screaming hairy armadillo, Six-banded armadillo, Pichi, Southern three-banded armadillo, Giant armadillo	9
Temperature seasonality	Pink fairy armadillo, Maned sloth, Silky anteater, Three-banded armadillo, Six-banded armadillo, Southern three-banded armadillo	6
Precipitation seasonality	Andean hairy armadillo, Screaming hairy armadillo, Southern three-banded armadillo, Three-banded armadillo, Six-banded armadillo	5
Precipitation of driest month	Greater naked-tailed armadillo, Giant anteater, Maned sloth, Silky anteater	4
Elevation	Andean hairy armadillo, Large hairy armadillo, Three-banded armadillo, Six-banded armadillo	4
Mean temperature of wettest quarter	Chacoan naked-tailed armadillo, Southern tamandua, Greater fairy armadillo	3
Annual mean temperature	Giant anteater, Giant armadillo, Southern three-banded armadillo	3
Seasonality	Maned sloth, Nine-banded armadillo	2
Precipitation of coldest quarter	Large hairy armadillo, Greater fairy armadillo	2
Minimum temperature of coldest month	Giant anteater, Maned sloth	2
Distance to waterholes	Three-banded armadillo, Nine-banded armadillo	2

Conservation Applications and Threat Analyses

18 (82%) reviewed studies discussed the conservation status of the species they were modelling, although only 9 (41%) studies assessed the coverage of Protected Areas (PAs). 20 (91%) studies discussed the implications of their results on habitat suitability, and 18 (82%) studies mentioned or analysed threats to the species studied. Threats that were often mentioned included habitat loss, climate change, habitat fragmentation, wildlife-vehicle collisions and human encroachment. 15 (68%) studies discussed recommendations based on their findings, which commonly focused on the prioritisation of hotspot zones and habitat connectivity, increasing the size of PAs, and encouraging further research into taxonomic knowledge.

Discussion

This systematic literature review identified 22 studies that used SDMs focused on xenarthrans in the Neotropics. The publication trend showed a clear increase in research activity, reflecting the growing application of SDMs in conservation biology (Guisan et al., 2013); however, the lack of standardisation across studies may pose a challenge for comparative work.

Geographic Representation

Although Brazil had the highest number of studies, Argentina showed comparable species representation across modelled outputs. Argentine SDM studies on xenarthrans are fewer but take a broader, multi-species approach, highlighting that countries with lower research outputs can still provide significant value to conservation. Suriname, Costa Rica, Mexico, and Bolivia were each the focus of only 1 SDM study; however, several other Neotropical countries where xenarthrans are present have not been the primary focus of any research fitting the criteria of this review. While some of these countries may be included in wider geographic SDMs (e.g., Rocha et al. 2022; Feijo et al., 2022), the lack of focused studies indicates a clear geographic bias in research focus. This underrepresentation cannot be explained by species richness alone; for example, countries such as Costa Rica support multiple xenarthran species (Lloyd et al., 2024; Santos et al., 2019). More likely, this underrepresentation stems from unequal research capacity, funding, and access to digitised data across the Neotropics, which are factors that can limit a country's integration into global conservation efforts (Meyer et al., 2015; Bowler et al., 2024). Moreover, research tends to focus on countries with strong academic and funding capabilities (Zhang et al., 2023a); countries with a higher GDP per capita often produce more conservation-related publications (Doi and Takahara, 2016). This pattern is also influenced by language and publishing bias

(Amano, Gonzalez-Varo, and Sutherland, 2016; Horchani, 2025). As a whole, these findings demonstrate how resource accessibility can shape the focus of xenarthran SDM research; this highlights the need to address systemic imbalances across the Neotropics to improve region-wide conservation management.

Species Selection

The giant anteater was the most studied species across all reviewed papers. The species is currently listed as Vulnerable on the IUCN Red List (Miranda et al., 2025), making it a likely candidate for ecological modelling (Vasconcelos et al., 2024). However, other xenarthrans with similar or higher conservation concern, such as the maned sloth (Santos et al., 2025), received less attention in the reviewed studies. This suggests that factors other than conservation status may influence study focus. Prokop et al. (2022) reported that large and charismatic mammals are more frequently studied due to the emotional responses they elicit in humans; given that the giant anteater is consistently labelled as such (Diniz and Brito, 2012), its frequent study may reflect a taxonomic bias. Beyond this, larger species are inherently more detectable and therefore more represented in citizen science (Roth et al., 2017; Mammola et al., 2023); this aligns with the finding that other large-bodied species were also frequently modelled.

Southern tamanduas were also a frequently modelled species. This may be due to their wide geographical range (Superina et al., 2010), which is a positive predictor of research effort (Ellison et al., 2021). The giant anteater and southern tamandua were modelled together multiple times, possibly as they occupy similar ecological niches and often occur in the same habitats (Desbiez and Medri, 2010); this allows researchers to classify them within the same functional group, which is particularly beneficial in SDMs for assessing how communities are affected by environmental change (Mayani-Parás et al., 2023).

The pink fairy armadillo was relatively understudied both despite and because of its Data Deficient status (Superina and Abba, 2025). Although this small extant armadillo is rarely observed in the wild (Borghi et al., 2011), knowledge of its susceptibility to stress from environmental disturbance (Superina, 2011) suggests that the pink fairy armadillo may be vulnerable to climate change. Further ecological modelling of this species is needed.

The 2 extant tamandua species were only modelled together once among the reviewed studies, despite being closely related. The scope of the reviewed SDM papers was often restricted to specific countries or regions (e.g., Abba et al., 2012; Astete et al., 2017), and thus researchers may overlook opportunities to compare habitat suitability among closely related species with allopatric distributions (Ruiz-García et al., 2021). Furthermore, northern tamanduas occur primarily in Central America (Navarrete and Ortega, 2011), a region that generally receives less conservation and research attention compared to South America (Urbina-Cardona et al., 2019). This helps explain the uneven representation of the 2 species in SDM studies, which in turn limits the potential to assess niche divergence within the genus. Overall, the imbalanced representation of xenarthran species in SDM research highlights how factors such as size and charisma influence the focus of studies, resulting in knowledge gaps for underrepresented taxa.

Data Sources and Variables

WorldClim (Fick and Hijmans, 2017) is a publicly available climatic dataset extensively used in SDMs (Cerasoli, D'Alessandro, and Biondi, 2022) due to its selection of spatial resolutions (Zhang et al., 2023b) and accessibility (Marchi et al., 2019). WorldClim was the most commonly used environmental variable data source in the reviewed studies; this is consistent with Bobrowski, Weidinger, and Schickhoff (2021), who noted that it is the most extensively used climate dataset for ecological modelling worldwide. The popularity of WorldClim may

also be reinforced by its use in modelling tool tutorials, such as the official MaxEnt tutorial (Phillips, 2017) and independent GitHub guides (de Alban, 2017).

There was a lack of standardisation in predictor variable selection for the same species, highlighting variation in scope and modelling aims across reviewed studies; this makes cross-study comparison challenging. However, 3 variables were often found to be most influential in relation to xenarthran distribution, including precipitation of the warmest quarter, temperature seasonality and precipitation seasonality. These variables likely capture the key climatic constraints on physiology and resource availability for these species. Salas-Elijatib (2021) notes that these are key factors in forest productivity, which is positively linked to ant (Kaspari et al., 2000) and termite (Guo et al., 2021) abundance, key components of xenarthran diets.

Literature, field studies and GBIF were the most commonly used occurrence data sources; this is consistent with the findings of a literature review conducted on SDMs for ticks (Kopsco et al., 2022), suggesting that this pattern is not xenarthran-specific. The wide use of GBIF is justified by its ability to provide standardised data and its alignment with FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) principles (Marques et al., 2024); this makes it particularly valuable for studies focused on countries with strict biodiversity laws, permit requirements or inaccessible areas. Collectively, the patterns in the data source and variable selection highlight the strengths of various SDM practices and call for increased standardisation to allow for comparison between study findings.

Conservation

This review found a strong emphasis on the conservation status of the xenarthran species studied, although this was accompanied by an incomplete integration of PA data. This may be due to consistent errors or gaps in PA spatial data sets (Visconti et al., 2013), as researchers may wish to avoid overestimating the habitat protection of vulnerable species. However, the

utility of SDMs in conservation is diminished when not rooted in policy or management decisions (McShea, 2014). Integrated SDM databases (iSDMdb) may help close the gap between ecological studies and conservation management by standardising and synthesising SDM outputs to inform broad-scale policy frameworks (Frans et al., 2021). The consistent link between SDM results and the implications on habitat suitability in the reviewed studies suggests that SDMs are being used as intended; it may be justified for individual SDM studies to remain focused on ecological questions, while iSDMdb serve as the primary tool for conservation prioritisation and policy applications.

Conclusion

This systematic literature review evaluated how SDMs have been applied to the xenarthran superorder in the Neotropics, focusing on studied taxa, environmental predictors and their application to conservation. 22 studies met the inclusion criteria. The majority of the studies were country-specific, with Brazil being the most studied country. The giant anteater was the most frequently studied species and was often modelled alongside the southern tamandua. WorldClim was the most popular source for environmental predictors, whilst occurrence records were primarily drawn from the literature, though GBIF is emerging as a credible source. Key predictors repeatedly identified included precipitation of the warmest quarter, temperature seasonality and precipitation seasonality.

The findings of this study suggest geographic and taxonomic biases, where research output is highest from nations with greater funding capabilities, and species are prioritised based on public appeal and size. Although conservation status was consistently mentioned in the reviewed studies, some lacked integration with PA coverage, which may reduce the applicability of SDMs to conservation management.

This systematic literature review has its limitations, including the exclusion of unpublished (grey) and non-English literature, the restriction to two databases, and a search string with particular modelling terminology. Although subjectivity was reduced by adhering to strict inclusion and exclusion criteria, the synthesis of results may have introduced bias.

Future research should focus on understudied, near-threatened or vulnerable species, such as the Chacoan naked-tailed armadillo (*Cabassous chacoensis*). Data Deficient species, such as the pink fairy armadillo, are less frequently modelled, and thus more field surveys are needed to gather population data. To strengthen the application of SDMs to conservation, SDM methods should be standardised, geographic coverage should be extended, and outputs should be brought together using iSDMdb.

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Appendix

Appendix Table 1. Reviewed SDM studies on xenarthran species in the Neotropics that were included in this literature review.

1	Distribution of extant xenarthrans (Mammalia: Xenarthra) in Argentina using species distribution models	Abba et al	2012	10.1515/mammalia-2011-0089
2	Distribution of the greater naked-tailed armadillo <i>Cabassous tatouay</i> (Desmarest, 1804) in South America, with new records and species distribution modeling	Rocha et al	2022	10.1080/01650521.2022.2085018
3	Land-use changes and the expansion of biofuel crops threaten the giant anteater in southeastern Brazil	Bertassoni et al	2019	10.1093/jmammal/gyz042
4	Species distribution model reveals only highly fragmented suitable patches remaining for giant armadillo in the Brazilian Cerrado	Ferraz et al	2021	10.1016/j.pecon.2021.01.001
5	Hiding in a Cool Climatic Niche in the Tropics? An Assessment of the Ecological Biogeography of Hairy Long-Nosed Armadillos (<i>Dasybus pilosus</i>)	Feng et al	2017	10.1177/1940082917697249
6	Surrogate species protection in Bolivia under climate and land cover change scenarios	Osipova and Sangermano	2016	10.1016/j.jnc.2016.10.002
7	Range shifts under climate change and the role of protected areas for armadillos and anteaters	Zimbres et al	2012	10.1016/j.biocon.2012.04.010
8	On the relationship between environmental suitability and habitat use for three neotropical mammals	Contreras-Diaz	2022	10.1093/jmammal/gyab152
9	Prioritizing road mitigation using ecologically based land-use planning	Ribeiro et al	2023	10.1111/aec.13295
10	Identifying hotspots and priority areas for xenarthran research and conservation	Feijo et al	2022	10.1111/ddi.13473
11	Living in extreme environments: modeling habitat suitability for jaguars, pumas, and their prey in a semiarid habitat	Astete et al	2017	10.1093/jmammal/gyw184
12	A conservation landscape for the Dry Chaco based on species habitat suitability	Cuyckens	2021	10.15451/ec2021-12-10.39-1-14
13	Climate fluctuations as a cause of rarity in fairy armadillos	Torres, Abba and Superina	2015	10.1016/j.mambio.2015.07.007
14	The Distributional Ecology of the Maned Sloth: Environmental Influences on Its Distribution and Gaps in Knowledge	Moreira et al	2014	10.1371/journal.pone.0110929
15	Occurrence of <i>Cabassous tatouay</i> (Cingulata, Dasypodidae) in Rio Grande do Sul and its potential distribution in southern Brazil	Oliveira et al	2015	10.1590/1678-476620151052235241
16	The potential distribution of <i>Cyclopes didactylus</i> , a silky anteater, reveals a likely unknown population and urgent need for forest conservation in Northeast Brazil	Machado and Miranda	2022	10.1017/S0266467422000372
17	Estimating potential geographic ranges of armadillos (Xenarthra, Dasypodidae) in Brazil under niche-based models	Anacelto et al	2006	10.1515/MAMM.2006.039
18	Safeguarding sloths and anteaters in the future: Priority areas for conservation under climate change	Borges et al	2022	10.1111/btp.13185
19	Reconstructing the distribution of Chacoan biota from current and past evidence: the case of the southern three-banded armadillo <i>Tolypeutes matacus</i> (Desmarest, 1804)	Ferreiro et al	2022	10.1007/s10914-022-09627-3
20	The effect of El Niño and La Niña episodes on the existing niche and potential distribution of vector and host species of American Cutaneous Leishmaniasis	Ávila-Jiménez et al	2024	10.1016/j.actatropica.2023.107060
21	Environmental factors affecting the distribution of three armadillo species (Xenarthra, Dasypodidae) in Argentina	Seitz et al	2016	10.1515/mammalia-2015-0084
22	Do the roadkills of different mammal species respond the same way to habitat and matrix?	Cirino et al	2022	10.3897/natureconservation.47.73010

Appendix Figure 1. Species combinations in multi-species studies. The x-axis lists xenarthran species, and the y-axis shows the IDs of studies that focused on multiple species; full bibliographic details of the corresponding studies are available in Appendix Table 1. Black squares indicate that a species was included in the corresponding study. The study by Feijo et al. (2022) was excluded from this figure as the species were not named.

Appendix Figure 2. Xenarthran species studied by country or region as mentioned in the literature. The study by Feijo et al. (2022) was excluded from this figure as the species were not named.

Appendix Figure 3. Spatial resolution of environmental predictor data used in the reviewed SDM studies. Original resolutions reported in arc-seconds or arc-minutes were standardised to kilometer units for comparison.

Paper Two

SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODELLING OF NORTHERN AND
SOUTHERN TAMANDUAS (*TAMANDUA MEXICANA* AND *TAMANDUA*
TETRACTYLA): RANGE OVERLAP AND FUTURE PROJECTIONS
UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE

by

SHANA B. KNIGHT

Abstract

Climate change continues to affect ecosystems and, as a result, species are increasingly pressured to adjust their ranges, behaviours, or physiological tolerances. Understanding these species' responses enables researchers to predict potential distribution shifts and develop informed strategies for conservation management. This study investigates the habitat suitability of *Tamandua mexicana* and *Tamandua tetradactyla* under current and future climate scenarios and examines the extent of climatic niche divergence between the 2 species. Presence-Only (PO) occurrence records and environmental variables were used to build Species Distribution Models (SDMs) in MaxEnt, and spatial analyses were conducted in R and QGIS to evaluate range shifts and overlap in suitable habitat.

The results of this research show contrasting responses between the 2 species. *T. mexicana* has a more restricted and fragmented distribution and is projected to gain suitable habitat under future conditions, whereas *T. tetradactyla* has a broader range and is expected to undergo a contraction in suitable habitat. These differences suggest that the species have diverging climatic tolerances. Despite their relatively recent evolutionary split, niche similarity measured using Schoener's D metric indicated low overlap between species, suggesting they have undergone niche divergence. Projected overlap of suitable habitat also declines under the future climate scenario, reinforcing the findings that the 2 species respond independently to climate change.

T. mexicana and *T. tetradactyla* are both currently listed as Least Concern in the IUCN Red List; however, the limited ecological connectivity between current and future suitable habitat could increase future vulnerability. Conservation management should account for species-specific environmental responses and address ecological connectivity to better support climate-driven range shifts. This study highlights the value of combining ecological niche

modelling with species' evolutionary context to better understand and manage species under climate change.

Introduction

Background

Understanding where species occur and the factors driving their distribution is fundamental to conserving vulnerable species, particularly in the current era of accelerating environmental change. An objective of ecological research is to advance the knowledge of species distributions, as they can offer insights into the interactions between species and their environments (Elith and Leathwick, 2009). Climate change is among the most influential forces behind recent distributional shifts, especially rising temperatures and altered precipitation patterns (Rubenstein et al., 2023). Numerous studies have documented a wide range of species shifting their ranges in search of more favourable climatic conditions (Parmesan et al., 1999; Chen et al., 2011); as a result, new zones of contact between previously non-overlapping species may form (Parmesan, 2006), and existing species interactions may be disrupted (Tylianakis et al., 2008).

As specialised ant and termite feeders, tamanduas play a crucial ecological role in tropical forests; however, little is known about how their ranges might respond to climate change. The 2 extant species, the northern tamandua (*Tamandua mexicana*) and the southern tamandua (*Tamandua tetradactyla*), are morphologically and behaviourally alike (Asencio et al., 2025), though they occupy largely allopatric distributions. *T. mexicana* ranges from southern Mexico into the northwestern Andean region in South America (Navarrete and Ortega, 2011), whilst *T. tetradactyla* is present in central and northern South America, primarily east of the Andes (Hayssen, 2011). Molecular analyses estimate that the 2 modern tamandua species diverged from one another approximately 2 million years ago (Coimbra et al., 2017), likely due to the Andean uplift causing their geographic separation (Gibb et al., 2016; Hoorn, Palazzesi, and Silvestro, 2022). Despite this divergence, the species remain ecologically

similar (Alfieri et al., 2022), although no studies have quantified the climatic niche overlap or divergence between *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla* (Moraes-Barros and Arteaga, 2015).

Species Distribution Modelling

Species Distribution Models (SDMs) are often used to model the potential range of species by associating species occurrence with respective environmental conditions (Gomes et al., 2018; Rios et al., 2024). SDMs are powerful tools, allowing researchers to identify species' natural distributions, predict suitable habitats in unsampled regions and forecast shifts in species distribution under environmental change (Elith and Leathwick, 2009). Various algorithms can be used to build SDMs; among these, MaxEnt (Phillips, Dudík, and Schapire, 2023) is a popular and high-performing algorithm, particularly well-suited to scenarios where Presence-Only (PO) data is available for the studied species (Valalvi et al., 2021).

MaxEnt (short for “Maximum Entropy”) is a correlative modelling method (Phillips, Dudik and Schapire, 2004), which estimates species distributions by comparing known PO occurrences with background environmental conditions (Merow, Smith and Silander, 2013). Following the training of the model, MaxEnt offers built-in tools to evaluate the model, one of which is a resampling procedure, ‘jackknifing’, where variables are removed individually to determine their influence on the model’s performance (Sinharay, 2010). K-fold cross-validation can also be specified as part of the evaluation by splitting the data, training the model on different training/testing splits, and averaging performance (Yates et al., 2022). MaxEnt then produces an output of both training and test Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve (AUC) scores, a measure of the model’s ability to distinguish between suitable and unsuitable conditions (Çorbacioğlu and Aksel, 2023).

Niche Conservatism

Although *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla* have been geographically separated by the Andes for approximately 2 million years (Coimbra et al., 2017), they remain ecologically and morphologically similar, raising the question of whether they have retained similar environmental requirements. Niche conservatism refers to the persistence of ancestral ecological traits in descendant species (Wiens and Graham, 2005). Niche similarity, the extent to which 2 closely related species share similar ecological niches (Warren, Glor, and Turelli, 2008), can be tested using a similarity metric called Schoener's D (Schoener, 1968). This metric quantifies niche overlap of the species across a climatic space by assessing whether one species' niche can predict the other's (Broennimann et al., 2011). As seen in various ecological niche studies (Russo et al., 2014; Qiao et al., 2019), niche similarity is often measured based on habitat suitability predictions from SDMs.

Aims and Objectives

To explore the ecological and geographical dynamics of *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla*, this study aims to use SDMs and niche similarity analyses. Specifically, it addresses 3 main objectives: (1) to model the current and future distributions of both species and assess how their climatically suitable habitat may shift under a projected climate change scenario; (2) to evaluate the extent of potential suitable habitat overlap; and (3) to quantify the degree of climatic niche similarity between the species. These objectives will provide insight into the species' biogeographic separation, potential future overlap, and the role of evolutionary history in shaping their environmental responses.

Methods

Species Occurrence Data

Occurrence data for both the *T. mexicana* (GBIF, 2025a) and *T. tetradactyla* (GBIF, 2025b) were obtained from GBIF, covering the period 2016-2025. Records were filtered to return only those with coordinates, a present occurrence status, and no geospatial issues in the search. All processing was conducted in R 4.4.1 (R Core Team, 2024). The data were then cleaned to remove duplicate records, records with missing coordinates, and records with an uncertainty > 1 km. A world shapefile of terrestrial ecoregions was obtained from WWF (Olson et al., 2001) and spatially joined to the occurrence points. As xenarthrans only inhabit terrestrial ecosystems (Padberg, 2017), any occurrences that did not spatially intersect with any terrestrial ecoregion, due to coordinate errors, were excluded from further analysis. Although there are morphological differences between the 2 species (Hayssen, 2011), the GBIF species photographs are often obstructed by the environment; additionally, the species are unlikely to co-occur (Hayssen, 2011). Therefore, to minimise the risk of misidentification due to human error, occurrences in countries shared by both species were removed. This filtering may introduce bias and errors in the calculation of potential range overlap; this is considered in the discussion section. The occurrence records were spatially thinned at a 5 km distance to minimise spatial autocorrelation. After obtaining the environmental layers, only records that intersected with non-missing (non-NA) values across all environmental rasters were retained, as required by MaxEnt (Yackulic et al., 2012). As there was an unequal number of occurrence points for each species, a random seed value of 123 was used in R to select 120 random occurrence points for each species. Table 1 shows the number of occurrence points remaining at each stage of data cleaning and filtering.

Table 1. Number of occurrences for each species at successive data processing steps.

	<i>T. tetradactyla</i>	<i>T. mexicana</i>
Initial Records	5504	5136
After Cleaning	2131	2555
After Spatial Join	2130	2471
After Country Overlap	1148	592
After Spatial Thinning	493	322
Non-NA Environmental Data	128	172
Final (After Standardisation)	120	120

Study Area

The study area was defined by creating a polygon around all occurrence points and applying a 100 km buffer to ensure that no occurrence points fell on the edge of the extent. This buffered polygon was used to mask the environmental layers, both to restrict the model to an ecologically relevant space and to reduce computational demands.

Environmental Variables

To model species distributions, a set of environmental variables representing climatic, topographic, and anthropogenic conditions was used. These variables were selected based on ecological relevance, data availability and findings of the systematic literature review conducted prior to this study. All layers were resampled to a resolution of 2.5 arc-minutes, projected to WGS 84, and masked to the buffered study extent using the raster (Hijmans et al, 2023) and terra (Hijmans et al., 2022) packages in R. All raster layers were exported in ASCII (.asc) format, and missing values were set to -9999, a standard placeholder value for missing data in MaxEnt.

Additional preprocessing was necessary for a few of the environmental variables. To minimise multicollinearity across the 19 bioclimatic variables, pairwise Pearson correlation coefficients ($|r|$) and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) were assessed using the usdm

(Naimi, 2023) package in R. Highly correlated variables ($|r| > 0.7$) were considered redundant, and variables with VIF scores > 10 were excluded. This resulted in 9 bioclimatic variables being included in the model. Elevation was also included. A fire frequency layer based on satellite-derived burn data spanning 2016-2025 was also generated. Annual burn data were reclassified into binary values where 1 = fire presence and 0 = absence. These layers were summed to produce a single raster representing the total number of fire events during that time frame. Both % tree cover and % non-tree vegetation cover were included as predictors to capture vegetation structure, as even though $|r|$ was greater than 0.7 for these variables, the VIF was less than 5. The Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) was also included in the model. The EVI for each pixel was averaged over 2016-2025. Table 2 provides a summary of all 16 environmental variables used in the preliminary model, along with their respective data sources.

Table 2. Environmental variables used in the various SDMs, along with their descriptions, data sources, and spatial resolution. All variables were resampled to a resolution of 2.5 arc-minutes (~ 5 km).

Variable	Description	Source	Resolution
BIO2	Mean Diurnal Range	WorldClim v2.1 (Fick and Hijmans, 2017)	2.5 arc-min
BIO3	Isothermality	WorldClim v2.1	2.5 arc-min
BIO4	Temperature Seasonality	WorldClim v2.1	2.5 arc-min
BIO8	Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	WorldClim v2.1	2.5 arc-min
BIO13	Precipitation of Wettest Month	WorldClim v2.1	2.5 arc-min
BIO14	Precipitation of Driest Month	WorldClim v2.1	2.5 arc-min
BIO15	Precipitation Seasonality	WorldClim v2.1	2.5 arc-min
BIO18	Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	WorldClim v2.1	2.5 arc-min
BIO19	Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	WorldClim v2.1	2.5 arc-min
Elevation	Digital Elevation Model	SRTM via WorldClim	2.5 arc-min
Forest Integrity Index	Forest Landscape Integrity Index (FLII)	Grantham et al. (2020) via https://www.forestintegrity.com/	~ 1 km (resampled)
Land Cover	Consensus Land Cover Classification	Tuanmu and Jetz (2014) via http://www.earthenv.org/	~ 1 km (resampled)
Tree Cover	Percent Tree Canopy Cover	MOD44B.061 via AppEEARS (NASA LP DAAC, 2023)	250 m (resampled)
Non-Tree Vegetation Cover	Percent Non-Tree Vegetation Cover	MOD44B.061 via AppEEARS (NASA LP DAAC, 2023)	250 m (resampled)
Fire Frequency	Number of Fire Events (2016-2025)	MOD64A1.006 via AppEEARS (NASA LP DAAC, 2023)	500 m (resampled)
EVI	Mean Monthly Enhanced Vegetation Index	MOD13A3.061 via AppEEARS (NASA LP DAAC, 2023)	1 km (resampled)

Model Calibration and Evaluation

SDMs were generated using MaxEnt version 3.4.4 (Phillips et al., 2023). Both species were modelled simultaneously using the same set of selected environmental predictors to ensure consistency and comparability. All models were run using MaxEnt's default settings, aside from the enabling of 10-fold cross-validation to reduce overfitting, reduce bias in performance metrics, and allow for species comparison.

Jackknife variable importance analysis was conducted within MaxEnt to give additional insight into the ecological significance and independence of each variable, and variable contribution tables were generated. Background points were automatically generated by MaxEnt.

Current Climate and Future Projections

To model current and future climate suitability, the set of environmental predictors was restricted to the 9 bioclimatic variables previously selected through multicollinearity analysis. Future bioclimatic data corresponding to the same 9 variables were obtained from WorldClim v2.1 (Fick and Hijmans, 2017), specifically from the BCC-CSM2-MR global climate model (Wu et al., 2019), part of the CMIP6 multi-model ensemble (Eyring et al., 2016) under the SSP2-4.5 emissions scenario (2041-2060), at a spatial resolution of 2.5 arc-minutes. This model-scenario-timeframe combination was chosen as it reflects a realistic emissions pathway based on current global trends, and it avoids excessive long-term uncertainty. These future climate layers were used to project species distributions using the MaxEnt model trained on current climate data. To assess habitat suitability, suitability values > 0.5 were considered moderate-highly suitable.

Niche Similarity

Niche similarity was assessed under 3 scenarios: (1) current conditions using all environmental variables, (2) current conditions using only climatic variables, and (3) future conditions using only climatic variables. This allowed us to evaluate the influence of topographic variables on niche similarity, as well as to compare how niche overlap changes under the chosen projected future climate scenario. Niche similarity was assessed using the ecospat package in R (Di Cola et al., 2016), which calculates Schoener's D using the following equation:

$$D = 1 - 2 \sum | p_i - q_i |$$

p_i : the probability of presence for species 1 at the grid cell i

q_i : the probability of presence for species 2 at the grid cell i .

A value of 0 indicates no niche overlap, and a value of 1 indicates identical niches.

Results

Model Performance

Table 3. Model evaluation metrics for *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla* across 3 model types: (1) current distribution using all environmental variables, (2) current distribution using climate-only variables, and (3) projected future distribution using climate-only variables. AUC scores closer to 1 indicate stronger predictive performance; 0.7-0.9 = useful; > 0.9 = high accuracy (Swets, 1988). The future (climate-only) scenario does not include metrics, as these metrics require known occurrence records for validation, which are only available for current scenarios.

AUC (Train) is calculated for a model that fits the known data; AUC (Test) is calculated for a model that fits unseen data (validation data); Omission (Train) is the proportion of known presence points that fall outside of the predicted suitable area; Omission (Test) is the proportion of unseen presence points that the model does not capture.

Species	Scenario	AUC (Train)	AUC (Test)	Omission (Train)	Omission (Test)
<i>T. mexicana</i>	Current (all variables)	0.98	0.96	0.093	0.18
	Current (climate-only)	0.96	0.94	0.093	0.13
	Future (climate-only)	—	—	—	—
<i>T. tetradactyla</i>	Current (all variables)	0.92	0.86	0.093	0.19
	Current (climate-only)	0.86	0.81	0.093	0.13
	Future (climate-only)	—	—	—	—

Model evaluation metrics indicated strong predictive performance across species and model configurations (Table 3). Test AUC values ranged from 0.81 to 0.96, demonstrating high model discrimination. As expected, training AUCs were higher (0.86-0.98) than test AUCs, although these value differences were not large, suggesting that overfitting is limited. Whilst training omission rates were the same across species and models, the test omission rates were higher in the full-variable models compared to the climate-only models; this suggests that the inclusion of non-climatic predictors may have resulted in the models' reduced predictive accuracy on unseen data, and thus slight overfitting. All model test omission rates were < 0.20, which is considered acceptable in ecological niche modelling studies (Peterson, Papes,

and Soberón, 2008). The metrics suggest that all models performed well, with good predictive ability and minimal overfitting. The full-variable current habitat suitability maps of both species were not included in further analysis, as several environmental layers contained missing data in key regions, and the climate-only model provided a more complete prediction; the full-variable habitat suitability maps can be found in Appendix Figure 1.

Species Distribution Models

Figure 1. Current (A) and future (B) habitat suitability for *T. mexicana* based on bioclimatic variables. Warmer colours indicate higher environmental suitability. The map was produced using QGIS version 3.34.11 (QGIS Development Team, 2023).

The SDMs and habitat suitability under current and future conditions, using only bioclimatic variables, differed for *T. mexicana* (see Figure 1). The current model (Figure 1A) predicted a restricted distribution, with high suitability extending to several Mexican states, including Veracruz, Tabasco, Yucatan, and Campeche, as well as into Guatemala, Belize, and along the northern coast of Honduras. In South America, fragmented patches of high suitability were also predicted, particularly along the coast of Ecuador and northern Peru. Suitable areas are present in Mato Grosso Do Sul (Brazil) and extend into eastern Bolivia. Moderate-highly suitable areas (suitability >0.5) for *T. mexicana* cover 3.55% of the masked extent land area in the current projection.

The future model (Figure 1B) for *T. mexicana* continued to show the Tabasco state of Mexico as highly suitable and showed an extension of high suitability to the state of Campeche, areas northward into Guerrero and Michoacan in Mexico, and southward to Nicaragua. The coast of Ecuador and the northernmost part of Peru become highly suitable areas. Moderate-highly suitable areas for *T. mexicana* cover 5.91% in the future climate model; the suitable habitat area increased under the future climate projection.

Figure 2. Current (A) and future (B) habitat suitability for *T. tetradactyla* based on bioclimatic variables. Warmer colours indicate higher environmental suitability. The map was produced using QGIS version 3.34.11 (QGIS Development Team, 2023).

The habitat suitability under current and future conditions, using only bioclimatic variables, also differed for *T. tetradactyla* (see Figure 2). The current model (Figure 2A) predicted a broad distribution, with high suitability along the southern Brazilian Atlantic coast, particularly in the states of Santa Catarina, São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro, and Bahia. Mato Grosso Do Sul was highly suitable in this model, with suitability extending southward into northern Paraguay and Bolivia, just east of the Andes. An isolated patch of high suitability was also identified near the tri-border of Brazil, Colombia and Peru. A continuous strip of high suitability was recognised along the coasts of Guyana, Suriname, and French Guiana, while another suitable area was predicted along the coast of Belize and the Mexican state of Quintana Roo. Areas in Nicaragua and Honduras are also highly suitable for this species. Moderate-highly suitable areas for *T. tetradactyla* cover 17.84% of the masked extent land area in the current projection.

The future model (Figure 2B) for *T. tetradactyla* showed a reduction in suitable habitat compared to the current model. Under future projections, the suitable area will no longer extend into northern Bolivia, though it will shift southward to Paraguay and the Formosa and Chaco provinces of Argentina. The previously broader strip of suitable habitat along the coasts of Guyana, Suriname and French Guiana is forecast to narrow, confined mainly to the immediate coastline. In the future projection, Mexico has a limited extent of suitable habitat for this species, though suitable habitats remain in Nicaragua and northern Honduras. Moderate-highly suitable areas for *T. tetradactyla* cover 11.06% in the future climate projection; the suitable habitat area decreased under the future climate projection.

In the current SDM, *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla* share 1.15% of moderate-highly suitable habitat. These overlapping areas are located in Bolivia, the Brazilian state of Mato Grosso do Sul, northern Guatemala, Belize, the Mexican states of Quintana Roo, Veracruz and Tabasco, as well as northeastern Nicaragua.

In the future SDM, *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla* share 0.85% of moderate-highly suitable habitat; the shared suitable habitat decreased by 26% from the current-day model. These new overlapping areas are located in Guyana, Suriname, the Brazilian states of Espirito Santo, Bahia, Sergipe and Alagoas, Nicaragua, Honduras and Belize. They share minimal suitable areas in Mexico under future climate projections.

Variable Importance

The most influential predictors are presented here, though the complete list of variables is available in Table 2 (Methods).

For *T. mexicana*, the most influential variable by contribution was temperature seasonality (Bio4, 42.2%), followed by mean temperature of wettest quarter (Bio8, 26%) and precipitation of wettest month (Bio13, 9.6%). Permutation importance results were similar, with Bio4 remaining the top predictor (46.3%), followed by Bio8 (17.2%) and precipitation seasonality (Bio15, 13%).

In contrast, *T. tetradactyla* was most influenced by isothermality (Bio3, 32.5%), precipitation of driest month (Bio14, 31.5%) and temperature seasonality (Bio4, 9.9%). Permutation importance ranked Bio3 highest (29.1%), followed by precipitation of coldest quarter (Bio19, 15.5%) and Bio4 (12.8%).

A full summary of variable importance values is presented in Appendix Table 2.

Niche Similarity

Table 4. Schoener's D values and associated p-values for niche similarity between *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla* under current and future climate conditions.

	Schoener's D	p - value
Current	0.33	0.17
Future	0.37	0.16

Niche similarity between *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla* was low to moderate under both current and future climate conditions (Table 4). The similarity value increased minimally in the future projection, although in both cases the p-values were > 0.05 , indicating that the observed niche similarity was not significantly different from random expectation. The increase in niche similarity cannot be assumed to reflect meaningful biological similarity.

Discussion

In this research project, the habitat suitability of *Tamandua mexicana* and *Tamandua tetradactyla* under current and future climate conditions was modelled and compared, assessing whether climate change may lead to further ecological divergence.

Climatic Suitability

According to the future climatic projection, *T. mexicana* is expected to gain 66% more suitable habitat within the masked land region, with its suitable range extending southward into Brazil. In contrast, *T. tetradactyla* may lose 38% of its suitable habitat, with suitable habitat moving toward the Atlantic coast. Although many species show a trend to shift poleward or upslope in response to climate change (Chen et al., 2011), such patterns vary by region and taxa (Lenoir and Svenning, 2015; Parmesan and Yohe, 2003). This study's findings support that climate-driven range shifts can be multidirectional, consistent with studies that find species are shifting towards areas that continue to meet their climatic niches (Sorte, Williams, and Carlton, 2010). Moreover, in the tropics, elevational shifts are often more relevant than latitudinal ones (Lenoir and Svenning, 2015); this pattern holds for *T. tetradactyla*, whose projected southward shift leads into higher-elevation areas in southern Brazil. *T. mexicana*, however, is projected to shift into lower-elevation areas of Brazil, particularly the Amazon basin. The latter finding challenges the pattern of upslope shifts (Feeley, Stroud, and Perez, 2016), suggesting precipitation may be a stronger driver for *T. mexicana* (Espinoza Villar et al., 2009).

Niche Conservatism

Currently, the climatically suitable habitat overlap between the species is just 1.15% of the masked land extent, projected to fall under future conditions. Climate change, in this context, may reinforce ecological isolation by reducing areas of compatibility (Sexton et al., 2009;

Wiens, 2007). Peterson, Soberón, and Sánchez-Cordero (1999) reported niche conservatism among sister taxa over long evolutionary timescales. In contrast, this study's results show climatic niche divergence between *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla* over a relatively short evolutionary timescale, aligning with Summers et al.'s (2023) results on sister taxa grackles. It is important to note that other aspects of a species' niche, such as behavioural or temporal components, may still be conserved between the tamandua sister taxa.

Climatic Drivers

T. mexicana's distribution is most influenced by temperature seasonality and wet-season variables, consistent with its humid habitat. The species' high sensitivity to specific narrow climate windows suggests it has limited ecological flexibility and a narrow climatic niche (Slatyer, Hirst, and Sexton, 2013). In contrast, *T. tetradactyla*'s distribution is shaped by isothermality and is more tolerant of seasonal fluctuations. This reflects its occurrence in subtropical regions and suggests that the species has a broad climatic niche (Eguizabal et al., 2022). This finding aligns with Janzen's (1967) hypothesis that tropical species evolve narrower thermal tolerances due to the stability of their climates.

Tropical ectotherms with narrow thermal tolerances are especially vulnerable to climate change (Tewksbury, Huey, and Deutsch, 2008), which may also apply to tropical endotherms. Considering this research, *T. mexicana* may become increasingly vulnerable to climate change despite the projection indicating an expansion of suitable habitat.

Ecological Connectivity

Although the models project future suitable habitats for both species, many of these areas are ecologically disconnected due to natural (e.g., mountains, predators) and anthropogenic barriers (e.g., roads, agriculture). This is particularly true for *T. mexicana*, where vast distances between suitable habitat patches make natural dispersal unlikely.

Both species are currently listed as Least Concern on the IUCN Red List (Turcios-Casco et al., 2025; Molina et al., 2025); however, as highlighted by Foden et al. (2013), species that are not yet classified as threatened may still be vulnerable and require prioritisation in conservation. Maintaining ecological connectivity can be an important tool to support species' climate-driven range shifts. Hole, Young, and Seimon (2011) mention Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EbA) as a strategy that relies on natural ecosystems to moderate the impacts of climate change whilst maintaining ecological corridors. Although EbA was proposed over a decade ago, it remains a largely underutilised approach in the Andes and is particularly appropriate for facilitating species movement over shorter distances. However, for species like *T. mexicana*, where the distance between suitable habitats is relatively vast, more direct interventions such as assisted migration may be necessary in the future, as seen in other cases (Burbidge, Kuchling, and Olejnik, 2010).

Limitations and Future Research

Recognising the limitations of SDMs is essential, as they influence the confidence of the projections. Correlative SDMs are constrained by data availability and quality (Kearney and Porter, 2009); PO occurrence records are often spatially biased towards accessible areas, leading to underrepresentation in other regions and reduced model accuracy (Phillips et al., 2009). Although spatial thinning was used to minimise autocorrelation in the data, some spatial bias likely remains. Moreover, the exclusion of species occurrence records from shared countries may have resulted in an underestimation of potential species overlap. Future research should compare models with and without these overlapping records to assess the validity of range and overlap predictions in this study.

As Dormann et al. (2011) note, SDMs often rely on broad climate variables that may act as proxies for unmeasured ecological factors, which can misrepresent future projections (Austin, 2002). To address this limitation and improve model robustness, ensemble approaches that

incorporate mechanistic variables could be used (Kearney and Porter, 2009), though this is often unfeasible for species like the tamandua, where detailed ecological data is limited. Developing research suggests that functional traits, such as body size, can help predict species' responses to environmental changes (de Bello et al., 2021; Gonçalves-Souza et al., 2023), which offers a promising alternative to mechanistic data in future work. SDMs are also limited by their reliance on known occurrence records, which reflect species' realised niche, rather than their fundamental niche (Jiménez and Soberon, 2021). As such, SDMs may identify environments that species tolerate rather than their true climatic preferences, which could potentially obscure ecological similarities between the species. Assessing climate vulnerability requires integration of ecological and physiological data (Pacifci et al., 2015; Williams et al., 2008); correlative SDMs alone are insufficient indicators. Although physiological data for tamanduas are limited, understanding thermal responses is critical as temperature affects species' distributions via metabolism (Dillon, Wang, and Huey, 2010). Future research could combine tools such as biologging (Wilmers et al., 2015), infrared thermography (Tattersall, 2016), and remote sensing data to gather information on thermal tolerance. To address the limitations of this study, it is essential that sampling efforts in under-sampled regions are increased and genetic and behavioural information is integrated into models (Srivastava and Carroll, 2023).

Conclusion

This study explored how climate change may shape the future distributions of *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla* and revealed contrasting responses that suggest increasing ecological divergence between the sister taxa. Although *T. mexicana* may gain suitable habitat, its narrow climatic niche may leave it more vulnerable to climate warming. *T. tetradactyla* is projected to lose suitable habitat; however, the species may be more tolerant of climate change. These findings highlight that even closely related species can occupy distinct climatic niches and reinforce the necessity of considering species-specific traits when assessing climate vulnerability at the genus level.

Notably, the need for long-distance movement to reach newly suitable areas highlights a disconnect between habitat availability and accessibility. It may be a challenge for species to track their shifting niches without adequate ecological connectivity between suitable patches, and thus it must be a conservation priority.

This study supports the need for proactive conservation strategies that integrate ecological traits, address habitat fragmentation, and promote functional connectivity. Whilst correlative SDMs help identify areas of future habitat suitability, their predictive power could be enhanced by incorporating physiological data. As climate change progresses, focusing on the research and conservation of lesser-known mammals like the tamandua is important to help mitigate biodiversity loss.

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Appendix

Appendix Table 1. Area of suitable habitat (km²) for *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla* under 2 climate-only MaxEnt models: current and future. Suitable habitat was defined as grid cells with a predicted suitability value > 0.5. All area estimates are based on a buffered study region with a total land area of 17,507,800 km².

	<i>T. mexicana</i>	<i>T. tetradactyla</i>
Current (climate-only)	621,795	3,123,860
Future (climate-only)	1,034,790	1,937,020

Appendix Table 2. Contribution and permutation importance values for bioclimatic variables used in MaxEnt models for *T. mexicana* and *T. tetradactyla* under current climate conditions. Contribution reflects the relative influence of each variable during the training of the model. Permutation importance reflects the decrease in model performance (AUC) that occurs when the variable's values are randomly shuffled. All values are expressed as a percentage.

Variable	Contribution - <i>T. mexicana</i>	Permutation Importance - <i>T. mexicana</i>	Contribution - <i>T. tetradactyla</i>	Permutation Importance - <i>T. tetradactyla</i>
Bio 2	1.6	1.3	5.7	5.9
Bio 3	1.3	4.9	32.5	29.1
Bio 4	42.2	46.3	9.9	12.8
Bio 8	26.0	17.2	1.0	0.8
Bio 13	9.6	1.7	9.0	9.0
Bio 14	2.3	4.7	31.5	12.7
Bio 15	4.8	13.0	1.8	5.1
Bio 18	7.5	3.7	4.1	9.2
Bio 19	4.8	7.1	4.6	15.5

Appendix Figure 1. Current habitat suitability for *T. mexicana* (A) and *T. tetradactyla* (B) based on all collated environmental variables. Warmer colours indicate higher environmental suitability. The map was produced using QGIS version 3.34.11 (QGIS Development Team, 2023).

Appendix Figure 2. ROC curve showing the performance of the SDM for *T. mexicana* (A) and *T. tetradactyla* (B) under current conditions using all collated environmental variables. The red line represents the mean proportion of known species occurrences correctly predicted by the model, plotted against the proportion of the study area predicted to be suitable habitat. The blue shaded area indicates ± 1 standard deviation, reflecting variability among model runs. The black line represents a model with no predictive power (AUC = 0.5).

Appendix Figure 3. Cumulative threshold plots showing model performance across suitability thresholds for the current-day model using all collated environmental variables for *T. mexicana* (A) and *T. tetradactyla* (B). The x-axis represents the cumulative threshold of predicted habitat suitability values. The y-axis shows the fractional value, representing either the mean proportion of the study area predicted as suitable (red line) or the mean proportion of known species occurrences omitted (green line). The orange shading represents ± 1 standard deviation.

A

B

Appendix Figure 4. Jackknife test of variable importance in the current-day SDM using all collated environmental variables for *T. mexicana* (A) and *T. tetradactyla* (B). The x-axis indicates each variable's contribution to the model's predictive power.

Appendix Figure 5. ROC curve showing the performance of the SDM for *T. mexicana* (A) and *T. tetradactyla* (B) under current conditions using only bioclimatic variables. The red line represents the mean proportion of known species occurrences correctly predicted by the model, plotted against the proportion of the study area predicted to be suitable habitat. The blue shaded area indicates ± 1 standard deviation, reflecting variability among model runs. The black line represents a model with no predictive power (AUC = 0.5).

Appendix Figure 6. Cumulative threshold plots showing model performance across suitability thresholds for the current-day model using only bioclimatic variables for *T. mexicana* (A) and *T. tetradactyla* (B). The x-axis represents the cumulative threshold of predicted habitat suitability values. The y-axis shows the fractional value, representing either the mean proportion of the study area predicted as suitable (red line) or the mean proportion of known species occurrences omitted (green line). The orange shading represents ± 1 standard deviation.

Appendix Figure 7. Jackknife test of variable importance in the current-day SDM using only bioclimatic variables for *T. mexicana* (A) and *T. tetradactyla* (B). The x-axis indicates each variable's contribution to the model's predictive power.